

Sensors selection for Real-Time Recovery of Textile Dyeing Wastewater

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Introduction

Textile dyeing is highly water-intensive, with up to 200 L of water used per kilogram of fabric, especially during wet treatments and rinsing stages, generating highly variable and contaminated effluents (Yaseen and Scholz, 2019). Washing and rinsing baths offer strong reuse potential, yet quality-based separation remains difficult. Key reuse parameters include temperature, pH, conductivity, color, and chemical oxygen demand (COD) (Yin et al., 2019). Real-time monitoring of these parameters is essential for effective wastewater recovery. Dynamic control using online sensors significantly improves recovery efficiency and supports circular water practices (Moretti et al., 2024). However, sensor selection is challenging due to the harsh characteristics of dyeing effluents, requiring both analytical precision and operational robustness. This study aims to develop an algorithm that can manage wastewater flows in real time based on the characteristics of the wastewater. The first step is to strategically place designated sensors within the wastewater baths according to the characterization of the wastewater samples.

Materials and methods

The study was conducted in a textile dyehouse at the small medium enterprise (SME). The plant operates a batch dyeing process that uses a high-temperature (HT) machine. Samples were collected from all process baths involved in the fabric dyeing process, and the wastewater was characterized. The measurement of temperature, pH, and conductivity was conducted using a Hach HQ40d multimeter, while color measurements were taken with a Hach DR6000 spectrophotometer. COD measurements were performed using a test kit. Following the analysis of the results, the necessary criteria for sensors were determined.

Results and discussion

Characterization results

Figure 1 shows the baths used in the plant to dye 100% cotton fabric from a single recipe. The results of the wastewater characterization for each bath generated in the batch dyeing process are also shown in Figure 1. The results indicate that the wastewater characteristics of each bath vary. Furthermore, the characteristics of each bath within each recipe vary depending on the fabric type and dyeing requirements. Therefore, it is crucial to determine the quality of the wastewater using real-time sensors, especially for the recycling of rinsing baths, and to direct the wastewater to the appropriate recycling areas based on the results. Despite the wide range of sensors and analyzers available on the market for the purpose of measuring water quality conductivity, color and COD sensors or analyzers.

Sensor selection criteria

In the stage of selection of sensors, it is necessary to take into account the values measured in wastewater resulting from the dyeing process. Specifically, sensors that operate over a wide pH range and at high temperatures should be selected. These sensors can be tailored to specific requirements through custom fabrication. The selection criteria for sensors are summarized in Table 1.

Figure 1. Wastewater characterization for each bath

Table 1. Sensor selection criteria

Parameter	Determined Range in Textile Baths	Preferred Sensor Type	Selection Rationale
Temperature	35–90°C (up to 130°C)	High-temperature resistant	Suitable range: 20–150°C
pH	5.5 – 11.2	Potentiometric transmitter	Wide pH range: 0–14
Conductivity	1,550 – 39,000 µs/cm (can reach 70,000 µs/cm)	Inductive conductivity transmitter	Effective in high salinity conditions
Color	85 - 10,200 Pt-Co	Spectrophotometric transmitter	Multi-wavelength absorbance measurement
COD	200 – 8,000 mg/L	UV-254 sensor or analyzer	Fast and real-time COD estimation

Note: All selected sensors must be resistant to high temperature (up to 140°C) and chemical exposure. Stainless steel or chemically inert materials are preferred for sensor bodies.

Conclusions

The recovery and reuse of textile dyeing wastewater, particularly from rinsing and washing baths, offers significant potential for improving water efficiency and sustainability in the textile industry. However, the variability and complex composition of these effluents necessitate the implementation of robust, real-time monitoring systems for their recovery. The integration of online sensors capable of accurately measuring key parameters such as pH, conductivity, temperature, color, and COD is critical to achieving reliable separation and reuse of wastewater streams. However, the successful implementation of such systems is dependent on the judicious selection of sensor technologies that are not only analytically reliable but also resilient to the harsh and fluctuating conditions. It is recommended that future research continue to concentrate on the field validation and integration of advanced sensor platforms within smart water management frameworks for the textile sector.

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